

The Importance of Religious Practice in Building a Healthy Environment

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Abstract

Religion is an important part of life for many people. Even people who are not all that religious by nature consider it to be important. The question is why do they feel this way? The reason is largely down to the belief that society needs religion. As a society, we benefit from our collective religious beliefs. There are many people who would argue that we could not function without religion. This paper reviews the fact that why religion is an important and essential part of people's lives and what are the very beneficial aspects of religion on the quality of life and education and how it influences the overall health of families and societies.

Keywords: religion, quality of life, religious beliefs, society, education, family.

Introduction

Religion is a philosophy based on spiritual beliefs. It aims to dictate a canon that would help to heal the spiritual side of the individual and, eventually, it will permeate into the dynamics of life. The biggest reason that society needs religion is to regulate behavior. Most of the laws that we follow today have their basis in religious teachings. There is considerable debate as to whether or not religion is required to make us good people but what is beyond dispute is that the rules for what is acceptable for society are largely based on religion. Without religion we would almost certainly live in a different type of society, Religion can have great importance for a society for a variety of reasons. Depending on the culture and governmental style it can range from a simple influence to complete control of society. Both from an individual and social point of view religion perform the following functions:

- 1. It provides mental peace:** Human life is uncertain. He struggles for his survival amidst the uncertainties, insecurities and dangers, Some-times he feels helplessness. It is the religion which consoles and encourages him in all such time of crisis. Religion gives right to shelter to him. He gets mental peace and emotional support. It encourages him to face his life and problems.
- 2. Religion explains individual suffering:** Man does not live by knowledge alone. He is an emotional creature. Religion serves to the emotions of man in times of his sufferings and

disappointment. On God religion puts faith and entertains the belief that some unseen power moves in mysterious ways to make even his loss meaningful. In this way, religion gives release from sorrow and release from fear. It helps man to bear his frustration and integrate his personality.

3. **It inculcates social virtues:** Religion promotes the major social virtues like truth, honesty, non-violence, service, love, discipline, etc. A follower of the religions internalizes these virtues and becomes a disciplined citizen of society.
4. **Religion promotes social solidarity:** Religion gives rise to the spirit of brotherhood. Durkheim viewed that religion strengthens social solidarity. A.W. Geen also pointed out that religion has supremely integration and verifying force in human society. It is true that common belief, common sentiment, common worship, participation in common rituals, etc. are the significant cementing factors which strengthen unity and solidarity.
5. **Religion converts animal qualities to human qualities:** Religion inculcates the spirit of self-service. It demands that people should be charitable and benevolent. Through various religious experiences, he forgets the worldly life and problems. This experience suppresses animal desires and converts the animal qualities of a man to human qualities.
6. **Religion is an agent of socialization and social control:** Religion provides a model for living. It upholds certain ideals and values. The believer imbibes these ideals and values in his life. Religion can help youth generation to become moral, disciplined and socialized citizens of society. An organization like temples, mosques, church, Gurudwaras, etc. also control the behavior of the individuals at a different level.
7. **Religion promotes welfare:** Religion teaches to the people to serve the masses and promote their welfare. It gives the message that “the service to humanity is service to God.” For this reason, people spend money to feed the poor and needy. Great religions like Hinduism, Islam, and Christianity, etc. emphasize aim-giving to the poor and beggars. With the influence of religious belief, different religious organizations engage themselves in various welfare activities. Like spreading of education and opening up many charitable institutions like hospitals, rest houses, temples and to help the poor.
8. **Religion gives recreation:** Religion plays a charming role in providing recreation to the people. Religious rites and festivals are more or less performed in every religion which gives relief to the people from mental exertion. Similarly, religious lectures, bhajans, kirtans, musical concerts followed by the utterance of hymn, etc. gives much more pleasure to the people and provides eternal recreation.
9. **Religion increases happiness:** Ever since Aristotle outlined the goal of a sound civil order in his Politics, social and political scientists and social psychologists have been particularly interested in what makes human beings happy. Happy people tend to be productive and law-abiding. They learn well, make good citizens, and are invariably pleasant company. It turns out that the practice of religion has a significant effect on happiness and an overall sense of personal well-being. Religious affiliation and regular church or mosque attendance are near the top of the list for most people in explaining their happiness and serve as good predictors of who is most likely to have this sense of well-being. Happiness is greater and psychological stress is lower for those who attend religious services regularly. Those pursuing a personal relationship with God tend to have improved relationships with themselves and with others.
10. **Religion comes as a source of social cohesion:** Religion is the ultimate source of social cohesion. The primary requirement of society is the possession of social values by which individuals control the action of self and others and through which society is perpetuated. Science and technology cannot create this value. Religion is the foundation upon which these

values rest. Children should obey their parents, should not tell a lie, women should be faithful to men, people should be honest and Virtuous, are some of the social values which maintain social cohesion.

11. **Religion Strengthens Self-confidence:** Religion is an effective means to strengthen self-confidence. There are certain beliefs like 'work is worship,' 'duty is divine,' 'result in predestined' etc. which is found in various religions gives strength to the individual and promotes self-confidence.
12. **Religion improves family stability:** There is a growing consensus that America needs to pursue policies aimed at re-strengthening the family. The beneficial effects of religious worship on family stability indicate one way to help accomplish this. Professors Darwin L. Thomas and Gwendolyn C. Henry of Brigham Young University's Department of Sociology sum up earlier research on the quest by young people for meaning and love: "Research on love clearly indicates that for many, love in the social realm cannot clearly be separated from love that contains a vertical or a divine element. Young people see love as the central aspect of the meaning of life; they believe that religion is still important in helping form judgments and attitudes. Their conclusion: "family and religious institutions need to be studied simultaneously in our efforts to understand the human condition better."
13. **Religion causes marital satisfaction:** Couples with long-lasting marriages indicate that the practice of religion is an important factor in marital happiness. Indeed, David Larson's systematic reviews indicate that religious practice is the most important predictor of marital stability. Others have found the same result. Twenty years ago, it was first noted that very religious women achieve greater satisfaction in sexual intercourse with their husbands than do moderately religious or non-religious women.
14. **Religion prevents divorce and cohabitation:** Regular religious practice is the critical factor in marital stability across denominations and overrides effects of doctrinal teaching on divorce. Significantly, cohabitation before marriage poses a high risk to later marital stability, and premarital cohabitation is much less common among religious people.
15. **Religion and Social Breakdown:** The practice of religion has beneficial effects on behavior and social relations: on illegitimacy, crime and delinquency, welfare dependency, alcohol and drug abuse, suicide, depression, and general self-esteem.
16. **Religion is against illegitimacy:** One of the most powerful of all factors in preventing out-of-wedlock births is the regular practice of religious belief. Given the growing crisis in out-of-wedlock births, their effects, and the huge social and economic costs to government budgets, this should be of major interest to policymakers. The religious practices of parents, particularly their unity on religious issues, powerfully influence the behavior of children. Religious belief and regular worship reduce the likelihood of this form of family breakdown.
17. **Religion decreases crime and delinquency:** What is true for youth is also true for adults. Religious behavior, as opposed to mere attitude or affiliation, is associated with reduced crime. The practice of religion is good for individuals, families, societies and governments. It improves health, learning, economic well-being, self-control, self-esteem, and empathy. It reduces the incidence of social pathologies, such as out-of-wedlock births, crime, delinquency, drug and alcohol addiction, health problems, anxieties, and prejudices.

Those who perform religious services more frequently, on the other hand, exhibit the following profiles:

- They are more optimistic about their futures;
- They have better relationships with their parents;

- They are more likely to dismiss racism as an obstacle to reaching their goals;
 - They are more likely to have serious and realistic goals for their futures;
 - They are more likely to see the world as a friendly place in which they can achieve, rather than as a hostile world with powerful forces arrayed against them; and
 - They are more likely to see themselves as in control of their futures, whereas those who do not attend church are more likely to see themselves as victims of oppression.
- 18. Religion is against alcohol and drug abuse:** The relationship between religious practice and the moderate use or avoidance of alcohol is well documented, regardless of whether denominational beliefs prohibit the use of alcohol. According to general studies, the higher the level of religious involvement, the less likely the use or abuse of alcohol. Significantly, involvement in any religious denomination or group generally decreases the level of drug use regardless of whether the denomination teaches against the use of alcohol, although denominations that teach against any use of drugs or alcohol exhibit the highest rates of drug avoidance. It has been known, and replicated, that alcoholics with a religious background or strong religious beliefs are much more likely to seek help and treatment.
- 19. Religion prevents suicide:** The practice of religion reduces the rate of suicide, anywhere in the world. In fact, the rate of religious act predicts the suicide rate better than any other factor (including unemployment, traditionally regarded as the most powerful variable). Those who worship frequently are less likely to commit suicide than those who never attend.
- 20. Religion decreases depression:** Religion appears to reduce the incidence of depression among those with medical problems. For instance, University of Michigan Professor of Sociology David Williams conducted a randomized survey of 720 adults suffering from leg and hip injuries in New Haven, Connecticut, in 1990. Those who attended religious services regularly were less depressed and less distressed by life events than those who did not. This finding held across age, race, socioeconomic status, educational attainment, and religious affiliation. Religious affiliation alone did not have these effects, but religious behavior did. Younger people also tend to experience fewer of the anxieties of growing up if they are religious.

Policy Implications

The evidence indicates strongly that it is a good social policy to foster the widespread practice of religion. It is bad social policy to block it. The widespread practice of religion strengthens individuals, families, communities, and society as a whole. It significantly affects educational and job attainment and reduces the incidence of such major social problems as out-of-wedlock births, drug and alcohol addiction, crime, and delinquency. No other dimension of any nation's life, other than the health of the family (which the data show also is tied powerfully to religious practice) should be of more concern to those who guide the future course of our societies.

Conclusion

From the discussion, we know that religion is the central element in the life of civilization. Throughout the ages, it is proof of its values. It has been the propagator of basic values and ethical code which provide cohesion to society and integration to personality.

The available evidence demonstrates that regular religious practice is both an individual and social good. It is a powerful answer to many of our most significant social problems. Furthermore, it is available to all, and at no cost.

The practice of religion is good for individuals, families, societies and countries. It improves health, learning, economic well-being, self-control, self-esteem, and empathy. It reduces the

incidence of social pathologies, such as out-of-wedlock births, crime, delinquency, drug and alcohol addiction, health problems, anxieties, and prejudices.

One last reason that we need religion is that it gives us something to believe in. People need to believe that there is a reason for what they are doing and that there is a reason for life. Religion provides this for them. This is what gives people the desire to go out and work every day and to try to make the world a better place. They do it because they believe there is a meaning behind it all. This is largely down to religion.

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